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Self-supervised learning approach for heart sound classification

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Abstract

This study contributes to the ongoing efforts in leveraging computational approaches for remote monitoring of cardiovascular diseases based on heart sounds, paving the way for more efficient and accurate clinical decision support systems. We propose a model for heart sound classification pretrained in a self-supervised learning fashion using a collection of heart sound datasets recorded in clinical and non-clinical conditions. Self-supervised learning in the domain of phonocardiogram recordings was a key step that enabled the model to capture richer and more robust representations by leveraging in-domain knowledge, thus, improving generalization when the model was exposed to previously unseen data. Our model outperforms the baseline BYOL-A model pretrained on general audio by 4% in terms of balanced accuracy, and 5% measured by F1 score.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) currently stand as the primary cause of mortality worldwide, responsible for roughly one-third of global deaths (Chen et al. (2021)).

Cardiac auscultation serves as a first-line, non-invasive method for screening CVDs, allowing detection of structural heart abnormalities from heart sounds. However, highly proficient and trained cardiologists are required to reach the desired level of diagnostic skills with cardiac auscultation (Mangione and Nieman (1997)), prompting the utilization of computer-assisted systems for early diagnosis and treatment of CVD patients (Reyna et al. (2022)).

Early computer-assisted systems for classification of human heart sounds were based on classical machine learning approaches, such as Hidden Markov Models (Romero-Vivas and White (2002)), Support Vector Machines (SVM) (Jiang et al. (2007)), or self-organizing maps (Dokur and Ölmez (2008)). More recently, deep learning has been also playing a key role, either based on the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) (Dominguez-Morales et al. (2017); Oh et al. (2020)), the Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) (Latif et al. (2018)), or the combination of CNN and RNN (Deng et al. (2020); Fakhry and Gallardo-Antolín (2024)).

The development of automatic classification of heart sounds was often driven by benchmark challenges together with the open access datasets released for this purpose, such as the Pascal (Gomes et al. (2013)), the PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology Challenge 2016 (Clifford et al. (2016)), the Interspeech Computational Paralinguistics Challenge (ComParE) 2018 (Schuller et al. (2018)), with a sub-challenge on heart sound classification, and the 2022 George B. Moody PhysioNet Heart Sound Challenge (Reyna et al. (2022)).

In this paper, we pre-trained the model for heart sound classification in a self-supervised fashion using a set of six publicly available heart sound datasets, allowing the model to acquire sufficient domain-specific knowledge. We evaluated a performance of the proposed model on the CinC16 dataset used in the PhysioNet 2016 challenge, achieving state-of-the-art results.

Heart sound datasets

Self-supervised learning requires a vast amount of data to train the model. We have identified and collected all the publicly available heart sound datasets up-to-date, with the characteristics of the datasets highlighted in Table I. Six datasets (Pascal, HSCT11, CDHS, Ephnogram, Open Heart, CirCor22) containing 15058 PCG recordings in total were used for pretraining the model in the self-supervised fashion, whereas the CinC16 dataset was used for an external model evaluation. The CinC16 contains heart sound recordings collected from both healthy and pathological subjects labeled into normal and abnormal categories. As the official test set was never publicly released, we use the validation set to evaluate the model performance, which contains approximately 10% of the CinC16 dataset.

Employing diverse datasets requires harmonizing the recordings. All the PCG recordings were resampled to a sampling rate of 2 kHz. Given their length, the Ephnogram recordings were divided into 30 seconds segments, whereas the Open

Heart and Pascal recordings shorter than 6 seconds were concatenated with their copies to meet the feature extraction requirements.

Table I: Characteristics of the collected heart sound datasets.

	Participants	Recordings	File length [s]	Duration [h]	Dataset use
Pascal	NA	832	0.8 – 27.9	1.6	Pretraining
HSCT11	206	412	17.9 – 71.1	5.2	Pretraining
CDHS	76	3,875	15.0 – 34.1	18.1	Pretraining
Ephnogram	24	69	1,800	30.6	Pretraining
Open Heart	NA	1,000	1.1 – 4.0	0.7	Pretraining
CirCor22	1,568	5,272	4.8 – 80.4	33.5	Pretraining
CinC16	1,072	3,240	5.3 – 122.0	20.2	Evaluation

Heart sound classification

We have incorporated three transfer learning approaches for a heart sound classification, i.e., a feature extraction, fine-tuning, and training from scratch, with the aim to evaluate how the classification performance is affected by the domain used for model training – general sounds vs heart sounds. The Bootstrap Your Own Latent for Audio (BYOL-A) self-supervised learning model pretrained on the AudioSet dataset, containing over 2 million YouTube audio recordings, was used as a base model. The input data for BYOL-A were log-mel spectrograms, and the output was a feature vector with 3072 elements (Niizumi et al. (2023)).

When it comes to the feature extraction, the base BYOL-A model was employed directly, with only a classification head trained on the PCG recordings coming from the CinC16 dataset. In case of the fine-tuning, all the layers of the base BYOL-A model were unfrozen, and it was retrained with the PCG recordings coming from the six datasets (Pascal, HSCT11, CDHS, Ephnogram, Open Heart, CirCor22). In the training from scratch, the model with the same architecture as the base BYOL-A model, but with randomly initialized weights, was trained using the same six datasets as in the fine-tuning case. The same classification head as deployed in the feature extraction case, composed of a single hidden layer with the ReLU activation function, dropout layer, and an output layer, was used. The hyperparameters of the classification head were optimized via grid search with 5×5 cross-validation using the training CinC16 dataset, within the ranges shown in Table II. The model was trained with the AdamW optimizer, cosine annealing learning rate scheduler and binary cross-entropy loss function.

The evaluation was done with the held-out CinC16 validation dataset using the model with the optimal hyperparameters. Balanced accuracy, sensitivity (recall), specificity, F1 score and Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (AUROC) were used as performance metrics, reported with 95% confidence intervals determined via bootstrapping with 1000 bootstrap samples.

Table II: Hyperparameter tuning.

Hyperparameter	Range
Mini-batch size	16, 32, 64, 128
Number of hidden layer nodes	64, 128, 256
Learning rate	0.00001, 0.0001, 0.001
Number of epochs	10, 20, 30
Dropout rate	0.3, 0.4, 0.5

Results and discussion

The automated heart sound classification is an important task in cardiovascular diagnostics that could be used to assist healthcare professionals in timely diagnosis, risk stratification, and monitoring of cardiovascular conditions. In this study, we explored various transfer learning strategies, including the feature extraction, fine-tuning and training the model from scratch in a self-supervised manner, in order to accurately classify heart sounds into clinically relevant categories of normal and abnormal heart sounds.

Given that the training set was highly imbalanced, with over 80% of normal PCG recordings, cost-sensitive training with the weighted binary cross-entropy cost function was deployed. Class weights were computed as the inverse class frequency normalized to value between zero and one. By incorporating class weights into the loss function, the model is penalized more for misclassifying minority class instances compared to majority class instances. On the other hand, the validation set was rather well balanced.

Performance of the heart sound classifier using the feature extraction, fine-tuning, and training from scratch is shown in Table III. Even in a zero-shot learning scenario represented by the feature extraction, where the model is pretrained on the audio data coming from entirely different domain, i.e., domain of general audio (e.g., human/animal sounds, common environmental sounds, musical instruments, etc.), it is able to learn reasonable heart sound representations, proving the fact that low level audio features are indeed shared across different audio domains. When the model is exposed to the PCG recordings during the training stage, either by fine-tuning the base BYOL-A model pretrained on the AudioSet, or training the model from scratch on the six PCG datasets, it is able to leverage the in-domain knowledge, boosting the model performance with the best balanced accuracy (0.84), F1 score (0.83) and AUROC (0.91).

Table III: Performance of the heart sound classification.

	Bal. accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUROC	Precision	F1 score
Feat. extract.	0.80 (0.75-0.84)	0.73 (0.67-0.81)	0.86 (0.80-0.91)	0.90 (0.86-0.93)	0.84 (0.78-0.90)	0.78 (0.73-0.84)
Fine-tuning	0.84 (0.80-0.88)	0.78 (0.71-0.84)	0.90 (0.85-0.94)	0.91 (0.88-0.94)	0.88 (0.83-0.94)	0.83 (0.78-0.87)
Train. scratch	0.83 (0.78-0.87)	0.75 (0.68-0.82)	0.91 (0.86-0.95)	0.91 (0.88-0.94)	0.89 (0.83-0.94)	0.81 (0.76-0.86)

All the models were better at predicting the negative class ("Normal"), but failed more often to identify the instances of the positive class ("Abnormal"), resulting in the higher specificity than the sensitivity. This behavior can be also observed in Figure 1a. Since detecting abnormal heart sounds is clinically more relevant, the fine-tuned model with the best balance between the sensitivity and specificity should be preferred. Solid model performance is confirmed by the ROC curve of the best performing model in Figure 1b, with a good trade-off between the sensitivity and specificity at different threshold levels and narrow confidence intervals, indicating that the cost-sensitive training has solved the problem of the imbalanced class distribution.

Figure 1: a) Confusion matrix; b) ROC curve of the best performing model (fine-tuning with mini-batch size 32, 128 hidden layer nodes, learning rate 0.001, 30 epochs, dropout rate 0.4).

Conclusions

Our results demonstrate the potential of self-supervised learning in extracting informative features from PCG recordings and leveraging them for accurate heart sound classification. Through rigorous experimentation and evaluation, we have shown that pretraining or fine-tuning the model in domain of heart sounds with multiple PCG datasets recorded in different conditions (clinical and non-clinical) allows the model to capture richer and more robust representations by leveraging the diverse information, thus, providing improved generalization when the models are tested on previously unseen data.

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